

ChatGPT: A means to enable student critical thinking in large classes

Willie Golden

Business Information Systems Discipline, J.E. Cairnes School of Business & Economics,
University of Galway, Ireland

Abstract

Since its launch in November 2022, ChatGPT has raised a lot of interest with respect to its potential impact on higher education. This paper argues that it is important to not lose sight of the fact that it is a technology tool and of the need to educate students with respect to the strengths and weaknesses of this new technology. A fundamental tenet of higher education is that we enable our students to actively engage in critical thinking. This paper presents a suggested pedagogy of using a Student Response System in a large group teaching environment that enables students to critically assess ChatGPT in an interactive and engaging manner.

Keywords: *ChatGPT; large group teaching; active learning; student response systems; critical thinking*

1. Introduction

Since the introduction of ChatGPT 3 in November 2022 there has been extensive coverage of how this technology is a supposed ‘game changer’ for third level education (Rudolph, Tan, & Tan, 2023; Susnjak, 2022). On the negative side is the idea that students will make use of ChatGPT 3 as the composer of their answers to essay questions (Marche, 2022; O’Brien, 2023), especially in large classes where students are not individually known to the lecturer. As an educator with 30 years’ experience of teaching large classes about the impact of technology on organisations, I believe there are significant opportunities to incorporate the use of ChatGPT into our teaching to help students with their learning and understanding. One of the graduate attributes of the University of Galway is to develop the disposition within students for ‘personal responsibility and a commitment to lifelong learning.’ Our students as part of their lifelong learning will regularly have to critically assess the appropriateness of new technologies for information retrieval and be personally responsible for how they choose to use them. I believe that helping students critically evaluate ChatGPT is an important contribution we as educators can make to their learning – by helping them to assess the merits and limitations of this specific technology – ChatGPT – while also providing them with the thought process to critically evaluate other technologies they will encounter post-graduation.

2. Description of the Teaching/Learning Context

Large class teaching at University is not just a recent phenomenon (Gibbs, Jenkins, & Alan, 1992; Wulff, Nyquist, & Abbott, 1987), it has become commonplace in business education (Mesny, Pastoriza Rivas, & Poisson-de Haro, 2021) and is here to stay (Mulryan-Kyne, 2010). The key problems repeatedly identified with large group teaching are the decreased interaction between teacher and learner (Allais, 2014; Hornsby & Osman, 2014; Mantai & Huber, 2021; Zhang, Cheng, Lei, & Wang, 2022), the low levels of engagement, commitment and motivation from learners (Hornsby, 2020; Mantai & Huber, 2021; Zhang et al., 2022) and the difficulty of enabling deep learning / critical thinking (Cooper & Robinson, 2000; McKeachie, 1980; Mesny et al., 2021).

While large group teaching poses problems, these can be mitigated by the pedagogical stance of the lecturer to use active learning (Hornsby, 2020) and student involvement (Mulryan-Kyne, 2010; Prosser & Trigwell, 2014). One means to achieve such active learning is by using technology (Hornsby & Osman, 2014). Using a Student Response System is a specific technology that has been found to mitigate the problems of large class teaching (Cooper & Robinson, 2000; Golden, 2023; Heaslip, Donovan, & Cullen, 2014; Hill, 2020).

Each year I teach a first year module on Information Systems to Business Students at the University of Galway. The annual average registration for the module is approximately 465 students. The module is double taught by me, as the University does not have a lecture hall large enough to accommodate all 465 students in the one venue. Since 2016, I have used Student response systems (SRS) in the class to enable students to actively participate. In the current academic year, Vevox (www.vevox.com) was the SRS platform used. This platform allows for a variety of different question formats, including open-ended questions. The use of such questions is always commented on favourably by students as they believe it actively engages them and gets them to think about things, and when the class responses are shown to compare their thoughts with their fellow classmates (Blasco-Arcas, Buil, Hernandez-Ortega, & Javier Sese, 2013; Kocak, 2022; Mayer et al., 2009; Sun, 2014). The literature on best practice in using SRS regularly acknowledges the importance of correctly phrasing the questions so that they are engaging for students (Kay & LeSage, 2009; Mollborn & Hoekstra, 2010; Wood & Shirazi, 2020). Over my years of using SRS what I have found is students respond most positively to questions that are topical, require them to think and are discussed in class once they have submitted their answers (Golden, 2023). I strongly believe that the topic of ChatGPT is extremely suitable for questions via a SRS and that discussion of the students answers in the Information Systems module taught to 465 students alongside a demonstration of ChatGPT will be a very productive learning experience.

The four separate questions about ChatGPT that I would suggest asking the students via a SRS are:

1. How does ChatGPT come up with answers to questions posed to it? (If you don't know type in Don't Know)
2. Is ChatGPT a trusted source of information?
3. How well does ChatGPT provide supporting references for the arguments that it presents?
4. Will ChatGPT always provide an answer to any question posed?

2.1. How does ChatGPT come up with answers to questions posed to it?

The purpose of asking the first question is to help students to be active learners, for the majority of them it is likely that they will not really know how ChatGPT works and just raising that awareness within them, will increase their curiosity to know how it does actually work. The structure and format of the questions posed via SRS is very important (Beatty, Gerace, Leonard, & Dufresne, 2006; Lantz & Stawiski, 2014). From my experience of asking open-ended questions to large classes, it is important to emphasise to students that it is ok if they do not know the answer to the question – as that is the purpose of education: to learn new things. The responses are not identified with the learner when they are shown

ChatGPT: A means to enable student critical thinking in large classes

on the screen and previous research on SRS shows that this anonymity is very important to the learners participating (Heaslip et al., 2014; Kay & LeSage, 2009; Kocak, 2022; Wood & Shirazi, 2020). This anonymity resolves the problem of students being afraid to give incorrect answers, especially in large class settings (Hancock, 2010). In the questions I pose a significant number of students choose to type in ‘Don’t know’ and find solace in the fact that a lot of others in the class similarly don’t know. After showing their overall answers to the first question on ChatGPT – using the facilities within the SRS - I would then present them with the answer given by ChatGPT about itself (see Table 1).

Table 1. ChatGPTs Answer to: Please explain how ChatGPT comes up with its answers to questions posed (ChatGPT response on 24/2/2023)

As a language model, I generate answers to questions by using a combination of natural language processing techniques, statistical modeling, and machine learning algorithms.

When a question is posed, I first analyze the text to understand the intent of the question and the context in which it is being asked. I then use a variety of techniques, including language parsing and named entity recognition, to identify relevant concepts and entities in the question.

Based on this analysis, I generate a response using a combination of statistical models and machine learning algorithms. These models have been trained on vast amounts of textual data, which allows me to generate responses that are relevant, informative, and accurate.

The specific process I use to generate an answer can vary depending on the nature of the question. For some questions, I may rely on pre-existing knowledge or information that has been explicitly programmed into my model. For other questions, I may generate an answer based on patterns and relationships I have learned through my training.

It's also important to note that while I strive to provide accurate and informative answers, my responses are ultimately based on statistical patterns and data. As such, my answers may not always be perfect or 100% accurate. It's always a good idea to double-check important information with a trusted source.

The importance of questioning the models used is a key skill all students need to develop – as George Box said: “All models are wrong, but some are useful” (Davenport, 2013). The ability to ask pertinent and critical questions about computer models is an extremely important aspect of being able to properly manage the use of Artificial Intelligence systems

(Luca, Kleinberg, & Mullainathan, 2016; Martela & Luoma, 2021). ChatGPT is a piece of software which uses a Large Language Model to create text that mimics how humans construct text. It is a form of Artificial Intelligence. In order to be able to evaluate the output it produces, it is vitally important that the student understands how it constructs the text it creates. ChatGPT uses a large computer model which works by predicting the words and phrases it should type in response to a question posed by a human. It does this without any understanding of what it has typed. It mimics how humans write by statistical word association, but without logical understanding.

2.2. Is ChatGPT a trusted source of information?

A vital skill for students to learn is the evaluation of information sources (Bhatt & MacKenzie, 2019). One of the Graduate Attributes of the University of Galway is to be “able to make sense of complex information from a variety of sources.” Part of training students with respect to this is to have discussions with them about what are trusted information sources and the need to reference sources so that others can review them should they wish. Again, students can be helped to be active learners by getting them to provide an answer with respect to ChatGPT as a trusted source. My experience from using open ended questions such as this one is that being required to think about the question helps students enormously and they want to develop their own answer before seeing what others think. Similar to question one above, following discussion of the combined classes response to question two, I would use the output provided by ChatGPT with respect to this question as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. As a follow up question to the one posed in Table 1, ChatGPTs was asked: Is ChatGPT not a trusted source? (ChatGPT response on 24/2/2023)

As an AI language model, I strive to provide accurate and informative answers to the best of my ability based on the information available to me. However, it's always a good idea to double-check important information with a trusted source, especially when it comes to matters that could have serious consequences.

While I try my best to provide accurate and useful information, there may be times when my responses are not completely accurate or up-to-date. For example, my knowledge is based on data that has been accumulated up to a certain point in time, and I may not have access to the most current information available.

Therefore, it's important to use your own judgment when assessing the accuracy of my responses, especially if the information is particularly important or could have significant consequences. In general, I can be considered a useful source of information, but not necessarily the final authority on any given topic.

ChatGPT: A means to enable student critical thinking in large classes

(Text underlined, to highlight more important parts of answer provided by ChatGPT)

The text provided by ChatGPT, shown in Table 2, provides a key learning for students with respect to ChatGPT, and clearly puts the onus back on the student to make their own judgement with respect to the answer ChatGPT has provided. This is a key learning, they cannot abdicate responsibility for the composition of an answer to ChatGPT, rather their own judgement and understanding of things remains central.

2.3. How well does ChatGPT provide supporting references for the arguments it presents?

In order to introduce variety in the questions posed to students, the third question being suggested might be best posed on a 5 point Likert scale from Very Well to Very Poorly, along with a 'don't know' option. The act of entering an answer to the question requires the student to actively engage (Blasco-Arcas et al., 2013; Kay & LeSage, 2009; Lantz, 2010) in an evaluation of ChatGPT – they are no longer neutral observers, they are required to think and input their current understanding with respect to ChatGPT. Displaying the collective responses will provide a platform for discussion on the current state of knowledge of the class with respect to ChatGPT and this can be followed up by providing a relevant subject specific example relevant to the class.

In preparing this article, I asked ChatGPT three separate questions, all of the questions were on topics covered in my large group first year module. As part of each of the questions I asked ChatGPT to provide a specified number (five) of references along with the reference webpages. ChatGPT duly obliged – however, none of the 15 references (5 per question) existed. The inability of ChatGPT to provide references to support its arguments is a key learning that needs to be imparted to students. The reason that ChatGPT cannot provide the references is to do with how its large language model works – it is a language predictor model – it continually predicts what is the word with the highest fit to the previous words it has typed. As such, it is not programmed to focus on a sub-set of papers that are most relevant to the question posed. At present it appears to use the same model for coming up with references – it creates titles of articles – as a series of words - which its model calculates have the highest prediction of being created together.

2.4. Will ChatGPT always provide an answer to any question posed (Yes/No)?

Now that students have an understanding of how ChatGPT works they can be asked: Will ChatGPT always provide an answer to any question posed – allowing a yes or no answer. Once you have displayed the answer to this question, I suggest that you ask a follow-on question – 'Provide a brief explanation for your yes or no answer. Most SRS have the ability to show answers as a word cloud – which I would suggest is an appropriate way to display

the answers to the follow-on question. After the students have given their answers and they have been discussed, I suggest you take a fun example that works for the material you are teaching. Below is an example that works for my large group module, where I teach them about a project management process specific to Information Systems development – the Systems Development Life-cycle:

Table 3. ChatGPTs was asked to: Please write an essay on how Rag Week can overcome the deficiencies in the traditional Systems Development Life-cycle (ChatGPT response on 24/2/2023)

I'm sorry, but I cannot write an essay on how Rag Week can overcome the deficiencies in the traditional Systems Development Life-cycle as Rag Week is a term that refers to a week of fundraising activities typically carried out by university students in the UK and Ireland. It is not related to software development or the Systems Development Life-cycle. If you have a different topic or question, I'd be happy to try and help

So with the answer provided by ChatGPT, there is some assurance for students that it will not just write an answer on anything it is asked. There is also the additional assurance that it possesses significant amounts of specific detail – as evidenced by the fact that it has an explanation for what Rag Week, even if the explanation of Rag Week is to its historical context rather than its current context. Again, reiterate to students that ChatGPT is a large language model and takes as its starting point the language, words and entities used in the prompt given by the user. So what would happen if we slightly changed the question posed in Table 3 – substituting ‘project management’ in place of ‘Systems Development Life-cycle’. ChatGPT provided a 450 word answer – an extract of the answer (first and last paragraphs) is given in Table 4.

Table 4. ChatGPTs was asked to: Please write an essay on how Rag Week can overcome the deficiencies in traditional project management (ChatGPT response on 24/2/2023)

Rag Week is a week-long event that originated in Irish universities and involves raising money for charity through a variety of activities, including parties, competitions, and other fundraising events. While it may seem unrelated to project management, Rag Week can actually provide valuable lessons that can help overcome some of the deficiencies of traditional project management. In this essay, we will explore how Rag Week can help improve project management practices.

.....

In conclusion, while Rag Week may seem unrelated to project management at first glance, it actually provides valuable lessons that can help overcome the deficiencies of traditional project management. By incorporating the creativity, flexibility, teamwork, and risk management strategies of Rag Week into project management practices, project managers can be better equipped to handle the challenges of complex projects and achieve success.

Sometimes in teaching, the example given provides the learning without need for further elaboration!

4. Reflection on/Implications for Practice

As educators we have the privilege of being guides for our students' learning, even in large class settings (Arvanitakis, 2014; Prosser & Trigwell, 2014). This paper presents one pedagogical approach facilitated by the enabling technology of SRS (Golden, 2023) to help guide students to gain a personal understanding of ChatGPT and through this understanding to appreciate the limitations of this technology. In particular, through reflecting on the answers given via the SRS and the subsequent discussion in class, they will gain a better understanding (Draper & Brown, 2004; Premkumar & Coupal, 2008; Wood & Shirazi, 2020) that ChatGPT uses a large computer model, which at its essence predicts the words it should type in response to a question posed, without any real understanding of what it has typed. It mimics how humans write by statistical word association, but without logical understanding. As such, the less a student knows about a topic they ask ChatGPT a question about, the less they are able to evaluate the correctness and applicability of the answer given. The more a student knows about a topic before posing a question to ChatGPT the better positioned they are to critique the answer given, but the less likely they are to find the answer given by ChatGPT helpful. ChatGPT is a very good sentence and paragraph constructor, but the judgement as to its correctness lies with the human user of ChatGPT, not with ChatGPT.

The goal of using a SRS with the questions outlined above is to enable the student in a large class to be an active and engaged participant (Hornsby & Osman, 2014) in the creation and update of their personal knowledge about ChatGPT rather than being passive information recipients.

References

- Allais, S. (2014). A critical perspective on large class teaching: The political economy of massification and the sociology of knowledge. *Higher Education*, 67(6), 721-734. doi:10.1007/s10734-013-9672-2
- Arvanitakis, J. (2014). Massification and the large lecture theatre: From panic to excitement. *Higher Education*, 67(6), 735-745. doi:10.1007/s10734-013-9676-y
- Beatty, I. D., Gerace, W. J., Leonard, W. J., & Dufresne, R. J. (2006). Designing effective questions for classroom response system teaching. *American Journal of Physics*, 74(1), 31-39. doi:10.1119/1.2121753
- Bhatt, I., & MacKenzie, A. (2019). Just Google it! Digital literacy and the epistemology of ignorance. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 24(3), 302-317. doi:10.1080/13562517.2018.1547276
- Blasco-Arcas, L., Buil, I., Hernandez-Ortega, B., & Javier Sese, F. (2013). Using clickers in class. The role of interactivity, active collaborative learning and engagement in learning performance. *Computers & Education*, 62, 102-110. doi:10.1016/j.compedu.2012.10.019
- Cooper, J. L., & Robinson, P. (2000). The argument for making large classes seem small. *New Directions for Teaching and Learning*, 2000(81), 5-16. doi:10.1002/tl.8101
- Davenport, T. H. (2013). Keep Up with Your Quants. *Harvard Business Review*, 91(7), 120-123. Retrieved from <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84879680365&partnerID=40&md5=80fdffb98b8c105402e05385884107f7>
- Draper, S. W., & Brown, M. I. (2004). Increasing interactivity in lectures using an electronic voting system. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 20(2), 81-94. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2729.2004.00074.x
- Gibbs, G., Jenkins, A., & Alan, J. (1992). *Teaching large classes in higher education: How to maintain quality with reduced resources*: Psychology Press.
- Golden, W. (2023). *Student Response Systems: Enablers of active learning in a large class*. Paper presented at the Higher Education Advances (HEAD'23), Valencia, Spain.
- Hancock, T. M. (2010). Use of audience response systems for summative assessment in large classes. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 26(2), 226-237. doi:10.14742/ajet.1092
- Heaslip, G., Donovan, P., & Cullen, J. G. (2014). Student response systems and learner engagement in large classes. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 15(1), 11-24. doi:10.1177/1469787413514648
- Hill, L. (2020). Mentimeter: A Tool for Actively Engaging Large Lecture Cohorts. *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 19(2), 256-258. doi:10.5465/amle.2019.0129
- Hornsby, D. (2020). *Moving large classes online: Principles for teaching, learning and assessment*. Paper presented at the Pedagogy for Higher Education Large Classes (PHELC2), Valencia.

ChatGPT: A means to enable student critical thinking in large classes

- Hornsby, D., & Osman, R. (2014). Massification in higher education: large classes and student learning. *Higher Education*, 67(6), 711-719. doi:10.1007/s10734-014-9733-1
- Kay, R. H., & LeSage, A. (2009). Examining the benefits and challenges of using audience response systems: A review of the literature. *Computers and Education*, 53(3), 819-827. doi:10.1016/j.compedu.2009.05.001
- Kocak, O. (2022). A systematic literature review of web-based student response systems: Advantages and challenges. *Education and Information Technologies*, 27(2), 2771-2805. doi:10.1007/s10639-021-10732-8
- Lantz, M. E. (2010). The use of 'Clickers' in the classroom: Teaching innovation or merely an amusing novelty? *Computers in Human Behavior*, 26(4), 556-561. doi:10.1016/j.chb.2010.02.014
- Lantz, M. E., & Stawiski, A. (2014). Effectiveness of clickers: Effect of feedback and the timing of questions on learning. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 31, 280-286. doi:10.1016/j.chb.2013.10.009
- Luca, M., Kleinberg, J. O. N., & Mullainathan, S. (2016). ALGORITHMS NEED MANAGERS, TOO. *Harvard Business Review*, 94(1), 96-101. Retrieved from <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85003816207&partnerID=40&md5=86e25f6d72603b4b0be8dd8fb2bb7c1a>
- Mantai, L., & Huber, E. (2021). Networked Teaching: Overcoming the Barriers to Teaching Experiential Learning in Large Classes. *Journal of Management Education*, 45(5), 715-738. doi:10.1177/1052562920984506
- Marche, S. (2022). The College Essay Is Dead. *The Atlantic*, 6, 2022.
- Martela, F., & Luoma, J. (2021). Why AI Will Never Replace Managers. *Harvard Business Review Digital Articles*, 1-5. Retrieved from <https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&AuthType=sso&db=bth&AN=152542838&site=ehost-live&authtype=sso&custid=s6172330>
- Mayer, R. E., Stull, A., DeLeeuw, K., Almeroth, K., Bimber, B., Chun, D., . . . Zhang, H. (2009). Clickers in college classrooms: Fostering learning with questioning methods in large lecture classes. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 34(1), 51-57. doi:10.1016/j.cedpsych.2008.04.002
- McKeachie, W. J. (1980). Class size, large classes, and multiple sections. *Academe*, 66(1), 24-27.
- Mesny, A., Pastoriza Rivas, D., & Poisson-de Haro, S. (2021). Business School Professors' Teaching Approaches and How They Change. *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 20(1), 50-72. doi:10.5465/amle.2018.0018
- Mollborn, S., & Hoekstra, A. (2010). "A Meeting of Minds": Using Clickers for Critical Thinking and Discussion in Large Sociology Classes. *Teaching Sociology*, 38(1), 18-27. doi:10.1177/0092055x09353890
- Mulryan-Kyne, C. (2010). Teaching large classes at college and university level: Challenges and opportunities. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 15(2), 175-185. doi:10.1080/13562511003620001
- O'Brien, C. (2023, 27/1/2023). Trinity advises academics to adjust assignments in light of ChatGPT cheating threat. *The Irish Times*.
- Premkumar, K., & Coupal, C. (2008). Rules of engagement-12 tips for successful use of "clickers" in the classroom. *Medical Teacher*, 30(2), 146-149. doi:10.1080/01421590801965111

- Prosser, M., & Trigwell, K. (2014). Qualitative variation in approaches to university teaching and learning in large first-year classes. *Higher Education*, 67(6), 783-795. doi:10.1007/s10734-013-9690-0
- Rudolph, J., Tan, S., & Tan, S. (2023). ChatGPT: Bullshit spewer or the end of traditional assessments in higher education? *Journal of Applied Learning and Teaching*, 6(1).
- Sun, J. C. Y. (2014). Influence of polling technologies on student engagement: An analysis of student motivation, academic performance, and brainwave data. *Computers & Education*, 72, 80-89. doi:10.1016/j.compedu.2013.10.010
- Susnjak, T. (2022). ChatGPT: The End of Online Exam Integrity? *arXiv preprint arXiv:2212.09292*.
- Wood, R. D., & Shirazi, S. D. (2020). A systematic review of audience response systems for teaching and learning in higher education: The student experience. *Computers and Education*, 153. doi:10.1016/j.compedu.2020.103896
- Wulff, D. H., Nyquist, J. D., & Abbott, R. D. (1987). Students' perceptions of large classes. *New Directions for Teaching and Learning*, 1987(32), 17-30. doi:10.1002/tl.37219873204
- Zhang, L., Cheng, J., Lei, J., & Wang, Q. (2022). Facilitating student engagement in large lecture classes through a digital question board. *Education and Information Technologies*. doi:10.1007/s10639-022-11197-z